

COGNITIVE BEHAVIORAL THERAPY AS A TOOL FOR REDUCING DELINQUENCY AND ENHANCING PSYCHO-ACADEMIC ADJUSTMENT IN SENIOR SECONDARY STUDENTS FROM BONUS FAMILIES IN JOS, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the effects of cognitive behavioural therapy on delinquent behaviours and psycho-academic adjustment in students from Bonus Families in Jos Metropolis, Nigeria. The study used a true experimental research design with four research objectives, four research questions and four hypotheses to guide the study. Multi-stage random sampling was used to sample 246 students from bonus families in the study area from Government secondary school. The study used three instruments for data collection which are; Bonus family screening test, delinquent behaviour questionnaires and psycho-academic adjustment questionnaire. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics where mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and a t-test for independent sample was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance levels. The study revealed that cognitive behavioural therapy reduced the delinquent behaviours of students from bonus families in Jos Metropolis. It showed a significant difference exist between the delinquent behaviours of students from bonus families who were exposed to treatment and those who were not. From the result, it was recommended that Cognitive Behavioural Therapy should be used as a strategy for coping with students' Behaviours and delinquent issues from bonus students in Jos Metropolis.

Keywords: *Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT), Delinquent Behaviours, Psycho - Academic Adjustment and Bonus families.*

INTRODUCTION

The term bonus families are used in literature interchangeably with such terms as: Reconstituted, remarried, partnered, merged, synergistic, social parent and blended family. A bonus family depicts a picture of a single parent living with his/her biological children and another adult partner who is not a biological parent of the children. These children are neither from both adult partners, but from previous marriages which no longer exist due to divorce, separation or death. A bonus family, thus, is composed of an adult couple, married or single, living with at least one child born from a previous union of one of the partners. Bonus families therefore includes: a bonus father, mother, and their biological children -joining two sets of children together from different previous unions. Another set of children would be the one born by the current union. Consequently, in a bonus family, three sets of children may be found. Globally, according to Kison (2011); Zeleznikow and Zeleznikow (2015); Longbap (2023), the number of children living with biological parents have declined, whereas the number of children living in blended families has increased. These changes in family structure occasioned by death, divorce and separation, affect children's psychological well-being and academic adjustment. Children in bonus families are placed in a stage of

maladjustment, thus experience more social, mental, emotional and spiritual challenges, than children from two parents-intact families. Furthermore, literature has established a correlation between family types and overall adolescents' well-being adjustment (Amato, 2006; Amato & Cheadle, 2008; Hanior 2015; Longbap, 2023). Accordingly, family attitudes, such as over protection, rejection, lack of love, lack of prompt response from parents, lack of encouragement and discipline may give impetus to children indulgence in criminality. Some Adolescents in bonus families are more susceptible to both delinquent behaviours, such as substance abuse and psycho-academic adjustment, than those from intact families. This is however, not the case with every child in a bonus family. Children from bonus family have been reported to demonstrate jealousy and anger when their biological parents share time with new bonus partner. This can be worse if a child is having trouble forming own relationship within the new family. Bonus family members have some challenges adjusting and consequently might feel unsecured, disillusioned, hopeless, helpless and lonely (Coelho, 2005 in Hanior 2015). It can therefore be deduced from literature that Bonus family can impact on children in a number of ways more especially when such children may have little control over their personal affairs, decisions and choices. Such children might experience conflict, strained poor interpersonal relationships with bonus parent and siblings, broken emotional bonds with biological parents, unknown roles and expectations, lowered well-being and adjustment, lowered school achievement, initiative and security, loyalty problems, feeling of anger, confusion and betrayal. All these adversely affect the psycho-academic adjustment of children in Bonus families. These myriad challenges call for the dispensation of psycho-academic supports service, particularly empowering children from Bonus families with life coping skills, decision-making skills and reality therapy. All these have implications for Cognitive Behavioural Therapy of children from Bonus families. Shoemaker (2010), cited in Hanior (2015), opines that juvenile delinquency is an illegal act, whether criminal or status offense, which are committed by youths under the age of 18 years. Eke (2006) and Alfred (2018), identify two categorizes of delinquent behaviours that frequently feature across Nigeria. The first category include: criminal offences, such as stealing, arson, rape, drug offence, murder, burglary, pick pocketing, shop-lifting and armed robbery. The second category include; status offences such as, running away from home, malingering and truancy. The manifestation of delinquent behaviours by students has been a long-lasting problem in Nigerian secondary schools. Ajake, Etuk and Omori (2010), report that there is a high rate of complaint about students' delinquency.

The origin of juvenile delinquency in Nigeria can be traced back to the 1920s when youths' crimes such as pick pocketing and prostitution became prominent issues in Nigeria. This ugly trend led to the establishment of judicial administrative processes by the colonial administrators to deal with juvenile delinquents. It appears that the worrisome issue of juvenile delinquency still plagues the contemporary Nigerian society in a serious dimension (Muhammed, Salawu, Adekeye, Ayinla & Adeoye, 2009). The concept of psycho-academic adjustment refers to psychological and academic adjustment. The term adjustment is often used as a synonym for accommodation and adaptation. Its denotes the results of equilibrium, which may be affected by either of these processes. It is used to emphasize an individual's

struggle to go along or survive the social and physical environment. Hanior (2015), observed that there are two main aspects of adjustment to secondary school, namely: academic and social adjustment. Academic adjustment connotes how well students deal with educational demands which includes; students' motivation to complete academic work, success in meeting academic requirement, academic environment. Students are often uncertain of their abilities to meet academic and rational demands when they move from one level of education to another. Students, especially those from bonus families need to be assisted to develop coping skills, which will enable them, overcome the psycho-academic challenges encountered in the school. The pursuit of academic goals is the primary purpose of being admitted to high school. The psycho-academic adjustment challenges that students could face in schools include among others; test anxiety, isolation and rejection, name calling, mood swing, fear of failure, low self-esteem and negative self-concept. All these threaten students' adjustment in schools thus impeding academic success. Russel and Petrie (1992), as cited in Hanior (2015), in a study on academic adjustment of high school students concluded that, many students who succeed academically in high school do not show similar patterns of success in higher institutions. Guidance services were found to play a major role in assisting students to adjust adequately to school environment and to take heed to academic issues by developing time management and life coping skills for better performance. Cognitive Behavioural Therapy is a talking therapy that can help manage problems by changing the way people reacts and leave. It is an effort to change the thinking pattern which is a form of psychotherapy where a person learns to change personal perception, and how to see things differently in life. These affect behaviours and mood of students. Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) can help people with challenges ranging from depression to chronic pains. Cognitive Behavioural Therapy is a psycho-social intervention which aims at improving mental health of students. It focuses on challenging and changing cognitive distortions and behaviours, improving emotional regulation, and the development of personal life coping skills. It is a form of psychological treatment that has been demonstrated to be effective for a range of problems including: depression, anxiety disorders, alcohol and drug use problems among others. CBT is the blend of cognitive and behavioural therapies, it focuses on moods and thoughts, and it also specifically targets actions and behaviours. Secondary school students are more likely to become delinquents if there is no good structure provided for them in their families. Furthermore, a family is one of the strongest socializing forces in life, where children are taught to control and shun unacceptable behaviours, to delay gratification and to respect the rights of others. Conversely, families can teach children aggressive antisocial and violent behaviours. Hence family types can influence delinquency. Family generally encourages conformity of youths by monitoring behaviours, applying consistent discipline and developing parent- child attachment. Thus, any structural changes that negatively affect a parent – child attachment, will likely result to delinquency. Secondary school students, all over the world, are faced with the threat of family disruption. This disruption is essentially caused by either death or divorce of parents. In the past, death was more likely to disrupt families than divorce, but in recent times, the reverse is the case (Amato, 2006). Divorce rate account for the emergence of bonus families, due to one of the parents' departure and remarrying. If the previous

marriage was blessed with children, the new husband/ wife become bonus mother or father to the children. The new family is otherwise known as bonus family where one of the parents is not biologically related to the children. The “parent” in this context, is termed bonus mother or father. Intact family on the other hand, refers to families where children are brought up by both biological parents.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Children from bonus families are prone to delinquent, oppositional behaviours as well as Psycho -academic maladjustments as ways they could express dissatisfaction with the decision of their parents to remarry after the exit of one of their parents due to either death, divorce or with full separation. They resort to oppositional behaviours as defense mechanism against either the real or imagined fear that the love, care, guidance and cordial relationship they hitherto enjoyed in the home will be threatened or usurped by the advent of a bonus parent or siblings. Therefore, they get agitated and frustrated as they would not like to share space and family possessions with the bonus siblings or bonus parent. Worse of these behaviours is that they are suspicious of the incoming bonus parent thinking that the person was responsible for the fate that befell them and that the person was coming to reap from where one did not sow. The news of their surviving parent remarrying is not good news to them. Attempts to frustrate this move had resulted in behaviours such as feeling and expression of anger and hostility, jealousy, withdrawal from domestic routines, and in some heightened cases, frequent outing, keeping of late nights and associating with bad friends that are capable of impacting negatively on their psycho-academic adjustment in schools putting the entire nation at risk tomorrow. The degree of deviant and oppositional behaviours is a function of age as well as gender. The younger the children in the bonus family the more is the likelihood for cooperation and friendliness in the family. The older the children the more they feel threatened and marginalized and so are likely to withdraw to defending and protecting their position in the family. This is not a healthy development for mutuality and harmonious co-existence or relationship. Gender is also a determinant factor. Male or female children are likely to react to the decision of one of their parents bringing in a bonus member (parent). This is why this study added a dimension on gender. Religious organizations, social support groups and non-governmental organizations have mounted programmes such as gender violence, sex education, healthy family living, healthy relationship with opposite sex, dating and mate selection, inter-personal relationship, adjustment, how to develop good studying habits that geared towards addressing psycho-social and academic adjustment needs of children from broken homes, separated and single parent families, as well as foster homes, but with insignificant positive results. The situation seems more with children from bonus families. The question thus is, would Cognitive Behavioural Therapy help students from bonus family adjust, psychologically and academically? Secondly, would CBT help students resist pressures to indulge in delinquent behaviours? This is what has informed this study that is on the “Effect of CBT on delinquent behaviours and psycho-academic adjustment of senior secondary school students from bonus families in Jos metropolis, Nigeria. Bonus families provide new dimension to family life where children have to adjust to an outside figure that enters the family. The entrance of a half parent would mean another period of adjustment for children entirely. Out of all the family members, children

may be the most affected by the formation of a bonus family, who often do not have control over what happens in their lives.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following objectives were raised to;

1. Determine the delinquent behaviours mean scores of students from bonus families in the experimental and control groups.
2. ascertain the psycho-academic adjustment mean scores of students from bonus families in the experimental and control group
3. Find out the difference in the delinquent behaviours mean scores of male and female students from bonus families in the experimental group.
4. Find out the difference in the psycho-academic adjustment mean scores of male and female students from bonus families who are exposed to CBT.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. What are the pretest and posttest delinquent behaviours mean scores of students from bonus families in the experimental and control group?
2. What are the pre-test and post-test psycho-academic adjustment mean scores of students from bonus families in the experimental and control group?
3. What are the pretest and posttest differences in the delinquent behaviours mean scores of male and female students from bonus families in the experimental group?
4. What are the pretest and posttest differences in the psycho-academic adjustment mean scores of male and female students from bonus families who are exposed to CBT?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the post-test mean scores between the delinquent behaviours of students from bonus families who were exposed to treatment and those who were not.
2. There is no significant difference in the post-test mean scores between the psychoacademic adjustment of students from bonus families who were exposed to treatment and those who were not.
3. There is no significant difference in the posttest mean scores difference of psychoacademic adjustment of male and female students from bonus families before and after treatment.
4. There is no significant difference in the post test mean scores of psycho-academic delinquent behaviours of male students from bonus families after treatment

METHODOLOGY

The design for this study was true-experimental research design specifically, pretestposttest randomized control group research design. This design involves comparing the effects of a given treatment with other treatment and allows a researcher to draw an inference and observe the effects of independent variables on the dependent variable. In this design, one or more independent variables are manipulated by the

researcher (as treatment), subjects are randomly assigned to different treatment levels (random assignment), and the results of the treatments on outcomes (dependent variables) are observed. The populations of the study comprised of all public secondary school students from bonus families in Jos metropolis. 70 bonus students were sampled out of target population of 246 bonus students in the study area using multi-stage simple random sampling technique to select students from senior secondary classes. The instruments used for data collection were; “Bonus Family Screening Tests (BFST)”, “Delinquent Behaviours Questionnaire (DBQ)” and “Psycho-Academic Adjustment Questionnaire (PAAQ)” all were developed by the researcher. The BFST is a screening instrument used to screened students from bonus families in the study area. It has ten items with two rating scales Yes? No. The DBQ have 26 items with five points rating scales while, PAAQ comprised of 30 items with five points Likert scale with its corresponding values of SD to SA. Cognitive Behavioural therapy was used as the treatment package for the experimental group to see the effects of the independent variable on the two dependent variables. The content validity was used to ensure that the items represent and sufficiently covered all the variables of the study. To ascertain the content validity, the instrument was subjected to thorough scrutiny by three experts; one from Guidance and Counselling unit, one from Educational Psychology unit and one from Research, Measurement and Evaluation unit all from the Department of Educational Foundations, University of Jos. The experts were required to evaluate the validity of the items in the instrument by ensuring that they were clear, well comprehended, appropriate and evenly represented. The experts were guided by the research objectives, research questions and hypotheses. At the end of it all, a consensus was reached by the experts’ judgments. Their final judgments and constructive ideas and corrections were guides to the researcher in the administration of the instruments. Cronbach’s alpha reliability method was established for the three instruments (BFST, PAAQ and DBQ). Reliability test measured the extent to which an instrument produces the same results on repeated trials (Bolarinwa, 2015). It was the consistency of scores from measurement over time or across ratters. However, the results for a reliability coefficient index of 0.70 and above mean that the instrument was reliable, while values above 0.80 indicates strong reliability where the instrument was adjudged strongly reliable for use (Bolarinwa, 2015).

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

The analysis of the data was presented in tables one, two, three, four, five, six, seven and eight followed by interpretations based on the research questions and the null hypotheses

Answering of Research Questions

Research Question One

What are the pre-test and post-test delinquent behaviours mean scores of students in the experimental and control group?

Table 1

Pre-test and Post-test Delinquent Behaviours mean scores of Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	Pre-test	Post-test	Mean
N	Mean SD	Mean SD	Gain \bar{x} - Difference

Experimental	35	114.37	22.79	56.26	11.89	-45.91
Control	35	116.34	21.13	104.14	20.35	-12.2

Table1 reveals the mean and standard deviation results of pre-test and posttest delinquent behaviours mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The result for experimental group shows that the pre-test mean score was 11.37 with a standard deviation of 22.79 while the post-test mean score is 56.26 lower than the pre-test mean score with a mean loss of -58.11, indicating that there was change in the behaviours of students after treatment. Also, for the control group the mean score was 116.34 and a standard deviation of 21.13 for the pretest. In the post-test, the mean score was 104.14 and a standard deviation of 20.35 with a mean loss of 12.2. The findings showed that students in the experimental group had a lower delinquent behaviours mean score (56.26) after treatment using cognitive behavioural therapy as against those in the control group (104.14) who were not given treatment, with a mean difference of -45.91. This implies that cognitive behavioural therapy does reduce the delinquent behaviours of students in Jos Metropolis.

Research Question Two

What are the pre-test and post-test psycho-academic adjustment mean scores of students in the experimental and control group?

Table 2

Pre-test and Post-test Psycho-academic Adjustment mean scores of Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

N	Mean	SD	Mean Gain		\bar{x}	
			Pre-Test	Post-Test		
Experimental	35	80.94	19.58	119.31	12.48	38.37
Difference 35.25						
Control	35	76.31	17.39	79.43	18.49	3.12

Table 2 reveals the mean and standard deviation results of pre-test and posttest psychoacademic adjustment mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The result for experimental group shows that the pre-test psycho academic adjustment mean score was 80.94 with a standard deviation of 19.58 while the post-test mean score was 119.31 higher than the pretest mean score with a mean gain of 38.37, indicating that there were positive changes in the psycho academic adjustment behaviours of students after treatment. Also, for the control group the mean score was 76.31 and a standard deviation of 17.39 for the pretest. At the post-test, the mean score was 79.43 and a standard deviation of 18.49 with a mean gain of 3.12. The findings show that students in the experimental group had

a higher psycho academic adjustment mean score (119.31) after treatment using cognitive behavioural therapy as against those in the control group (79.43) who were not given treatment, with a mean difference of 35.25. This implies that cognitive behavioural therapy does positively change the psycho-academic adjustment behaviours of students in Jos Metropolis.

Research Question Three

What is the pretest and post-test differences in the delinquent behaviour mean score of male and female students from bonus families in the experimental group?

Table 3

Post-test Delinquent Behaviour mean Scores of Male and Female Students’ in the

Experimental Group

Group	Gender	N	Mean	SD	χ - Difference
Mean	Male	21	55.62	10.21	
	Female	14	57.21	14.40	
Experimental			1.55		

Table 3 reveals the mean and standard deviation results of posttest delinquent behaviour mean scores of male and female students in the experimental group. The result for experimental group shows that the posttest mean score for male was 55.62 with a standard deviation of 10.21, while the mean score for female was 57.21 with standard deviation of 14.40. It implies that the delinquent behaviour mean score of male and female students were almost same after exposure to cognitive behavioural therapy.

Research Question Four

What are the post-test differences in the psycho-academic adjustment mean scores of male and female students who are exposed to CBT?

Table 4

Post-test Psycho-academic Adjustment mean Scores of Male and Female Students’ from Bonus Families in the Experimental Group

Group	Gender	N	Mean	SD	χ - Difference
Mean	Male	21	119.38	13.68	
	Female	14	119.21	10.92	
Experimental			0.17		

Table 4 reveals the mean and standard deviation results of posttest psycho-academic adjustment mean scores of male and female students in the experimental group. The result for experimental group shows that the posttest mean score for male was 119.38 with a standard deviation of 13.68, while the mean score for female was 119.21 with standard deviation of 10.92. It implies that the psycho-academic adjustment behaviour mean score of male and female students were almost same with a mean difference of 0.17 after exposure to cognitive behavioural therapy.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the post-test mean score of delinquent behaviours of students who were exposed to treatment and those who were not.

Table 5

Summary of t-test result on Post-test Delinquent Behaviours of Students who were exposed to Treatment and those who were not

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t	P-Value	Decision
Experimental	35	56.26	11.89				
68 -12.02 .000 Significant Control	35	104.14	20.35				

Table 5 showed the t-test result of the post-test mean score difference between the delinquent behaviour of students who were exposed to treatment and those who were not. The result indicated that experimental group had post-test delinquent behaviour mean score of 56.26 with standard deviation of 11.89 while control group had post-test mean score of 104.14 with standard deviation of 20.35. The result further yielded $t(68) = -12.02, p < 0.05$. Since the pvalue of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. It was concluded that there was a significant difference between the delinquent behaviour of students who were exposed to treatment and those who were not. It means that cognitive behavioural therapy is effective in positively changing the delinquent behaviour of students. It implies that exposing students to cognitive behavioural therapy can positively reduce student's delinquent behaviours.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the post-test mean score of psycho-academic adjustment of students who were exposed to treatment and those who were not.

Table 6

Summary of t-test result on Post-test mean difference in the Psycho-academic Adjustment of Students who were exposed to Treatment and those who were not

Group	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t	P-Value	Decision
Experimental	35	119.31	12.48				
68 10.58 .000 Significant Control	35	79.43	18.49				

Table 6 showed the t-test result of the post-test mean score difference between the psychoacademic adjustment behaviours of students who were exposed to treatment and those who were not. The result

indicated that experimental group had post-test psycho-academic adjustment behaviours mean score of 119.31 with standard deviation of 12.48` while control group had a posttest mean score of 79.43 with standard deviation of 18.49. The result further yielded $t(68) = 10.58, p < 0.05$. Since the p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. It was concluded that there was a significant difference between the psycho-academic adjustment behaviours of students who were exposed to treatment and those who were not. It means that cognitive behavioural therapy is effective in positively changing the psycho-academic adjustment behaviours of students. It implies that exposing students to cognitive behavioural therapy can positively improve student’s psycho-academic adjustment behaviours.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference in the mean score of the delinquent behaviours of male and female students after treatment.

Table 7

Summary of t-test result on difference in the Delinquent Behaviours of Male and Female Students after Treatment

Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t	p-Value	Decision
Male	21	55.62	10.21				
			33		-0.384	0.703	Insignificant
Female	14	57.21	14.40				

Table 7 showed the t-test result on the difference between the delinquent behaviours of male and female students after treatment. The result indicated that male students had post-test delinquent behaviours mean score of 55.62 with standard deviation of 10.21` while female students had post-test mean score of 57.21 with standard deviation of 14.40. The result further yielded $t(33) = -.384, p > 0.05$. Since the p-value of 0.703 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was retained. It was concluded that there was no significant difference between the delinquent behaviours of male and female students after treatment. It means that cognitive behavioural therapy is effective in reducing the delinquent behaviours of both male and female students.

Hypothesis Four

There is no significant difference in the mean score of psycho-academic adjustment behaviours of male students from bonus homes after treatment.

Table 8

Summary of t-test result on Psycho-Academic Adjustment Behaviours of Male and Female Students from Bonus Families after Treatment

Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t	P-Value	Decision
Male	21	119.38	13.68				
			33		.038	0.970	Insignificant

Female 14 119.21 10.92

Table 8 showed the t-test result on the difference between the psycho-academic adjustment behaviours of male and female students after treatment. The result indicated that male students had a post-test psycho-academic adjustment behaviours mean score of 119.38 with standard deviation of 13.68 while female students had post-test mean score of 119.21 with standard deviation of 10.92. The result further yielded $t(33) = .038, p > 0.05$. Since the p-value of 0.970 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was retained. It was concluded that there was no significant difference in the psycho-academic adjustment behaviours of male and female students after treatment. It means that cognitive behavioural therapy is effective in positively changing the psycho-academic adjustment behaviours of both male and female students.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study showed that cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) is a treatment package that addresses issues on delinquent behaviours and Psycho-academics adjustment of bonus families' students from public secondary schools in Jos metropolis. It also indicated that (CBT) is a measure used in coping with student Behaviours modification issues in our contemporary society. It further showed that the participant in the experimental group performed better than those from the control group which signifies that the intervention package used will further enhanced the delinquent students to adjust both academically and psychologically in their school performance. The findings also indicated that students in the experimental group had a lower delinquent behaviours mean score of (56.26) after treatment using cognitive behavioural therapy as against those in the control group (104.14) who were not given treatment, with a mean difference of -45.91. This implies that cognitive behavioural therapy does reduce the delinquent behaviours of students from bonus families in Jos metropolis. It showed that a significant difference exists between the delinquent behaviours of students from bonus families who were exposed to treatment and those who were not. The findings also indicated that students in the experimental group had a higher psycho academic adjustment mean score of (119.31) after treatment using cognitive behavioural therapy as against those in the control group (79.43) who were not given treatment, with a mean difference of 35.25. This implies that cognitive behavioural therapy does positively change the psychoacademic adjustment behaviours of students from bonus families in Jos Metropolis. It further showed a significant difference between the psycho-academic adjustment behaviours of students from bonus families who were exposed to treatment and those who were not. The results also indicated that the delinquent behaviours mean score of male and female students were almost same after exposure to cognitive behavioural therapy. Indicating that there was no significant difference between the delinquent behaviours of male and female students from bonus families who were exposed to treatment. The results showed that the psycho-academic adjustment behaviours mean score of male and female students were almost same with a mean difference of 0.17 after exposure to cognitive behavioural therapy. Indicating that there was no significant

difference between the psychoacademic adjustment behaviours of male and female students from bonus families who were exposed to treatment.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of this study, it is concluded that cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) is a treatment package that addresses issues on delinquent behaviours and Psycho-academics adjustment of bonus families' students from public secondary schools in Jos metropolis. Also (CBT) is a measure used in coping with student Behaviours modification issues in our contemporary society. The intervention package used will further enhance the delinquent students to adjust both academically and psychologically in their school performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made:

1. Counselling Centre's should use cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) as model to cope with students' behavioural modifications
2. Bonus students should be given a fair treatment academically and psychologically both at home and in schools to enable them adjust delinquent behaviours that affect their school activities.
3. Longitudinal and gender-based studies on psychological adjustment of children from bonus families are needed to generate sufficient data on programme intervention in Nigeria.
4. Government should bring policies that will check mate's families that humiliate children irrespective of where they come from in order to curtail delinquent behaviours of students and improve their academic adjustments.
5. Bonus family's students should acquire lifelong coping skills to enable them become selfreliance, gain self-confidence, self-worth, self-efficacy set and purse realistic life goals.

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